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**FANDOM AS SIMULACRUM:
DIGITAL MYTHMAKING AND THE POLITICS OF CANON**

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RESUME

Cette thèse examine les dynamiques culturelles, émotionnelles et symboliques de l'écriture de fanfiction d'un point de vue sociologique, en se concentrant particulièrement sur la manière dont les communautés de fans construisent, diffusent et stabilisent collectivement leurs interprétations des personnages. S'appuyant sur des entretiens semi-structurés avec dix auteurs de fanfiction affiliés à la communauté Marvel Trumps Hate (MTH) et à plusieurs autres fandoms, cette étude examine comment le fanon s'écarte non seulement du canon, mais devient également une réalité émotionnelle et narrative partagée.

L'argument principal de la thèse est développé à travers le cadre conceptuel de l'hyperréalité théorisé par Jean Baudrillard. Plutôt que de considérer la fanfiction comme dérivée ou sous-culturelle, cette étude la présente comme un lieu où les réalités simulées, produites par la répétition, le consensus communautaire et la cohérence affective, remplacent l'autorité du texte original. Les auteurs soulignent à plusieurs reprises que même dans les fanfictions d'univers alternatifs (AU), la cohérence émotionnelle doit être préservée et les motivations des personnages doivent être justifiées sur le plan narratif. Dans les méga-fandoms tels que Marvel et Harry Potter, ces constructions fanon deviennent parfois plus réelles que le canon : elles sont référencées, débattues et vécues émotionnellement par certaines communautés.

La recherche examine également comment le capital culturel opère au sein des communautés de fans à travers la productivité, la sélection des tropes, le timing et la participation communautaire. En outre, la thèse positionne la fanfiction comme une forme de résistance émotionnelle et politique : un espace où les relations alternatives, les identités queer et les vérités émotionnelles sont mises en avant à travers des pratiques narratives collectives.

En fin de compte, cette étude présente la fanfiction comme un espace discursif et émotionnel où les lecteurs et les auteurs collaborent pour créer un ordre symbolique hyperréaliste, où la légitimité narrative ne repose plus sur la paternité de l'œuvre, mais sur la résonance émotionnelle et la simulation collective.

ABSTRACT

This thesis investigates the cultural, emotional, and symbolic dynamics of fan fiction writing from a sociological perspective, focusing in particular on how fan communities collectively construct, circulate, and stabilize character interpretations. Drawing on semi-structured interviews with ten fan fiction writers affiliated with the Marvel Trumps Hate (MTH) community and several other fandoms, this study investigates how fanon not only deviates from canon but also becomes a shared emotional and narrative reality.

The thesis's main argument is developed through the conceptual framework of hyperreality theorised by Jean Baudrillard. Rather than viewing fanfiction as derivative or subcultural, this study frames it as a site where simulated realities, produced through repetition, community consensus, and affective coherence, displace the authority of the original text. Writers repeatedly emphasize that even in alternate universe fanfics (AUs), emotional consistency must be preserved, and character motivations must be narratively justified. In mega-fandoms such as Marvel and Harry Potter, these fanon constructs time to time become more real than canon—referenced, debated, and emotionally lived by certain communities.

The research also examines how cultural capital operates within fan communities through productivity, trope selection, timing, and community participation. Furthermore, the thesis positions fan fiction as an emotional and political form of resistance: a space where alternative relationships, queer identities, and emotional truths are foregrounded through collective storytelling practices.

Ultimately, this study presents fan fiction as a discursive and emotional space where readers and writers collaborate to create a hyperreal symbolic order, where narrative legitimacy no longer rests on authorship but on emotional resonance and collective simulation.

ÖZET

Bu tez, sosyolojik bir bakış açısıyla fan kurgu yazımının kültürel, duygusal ve sembolik dinamiklerini araştırıyor ve özellikle fan topluluklarının karakter yorumlarını toplu olarak nasıl oluşturduklarına, yaydıklarına ve sabitlediklerine odaklanıyor. Marvel Trumps Hate (MTH) alt grubuna bağlı olan birçok fan kurgu yazarıyla yapılan yarı yapılandırılmış görüşmelerden yararlanarak, bu çalışma fanonun kanondan sadece sapmakla kalmayıp, nasıl ortak bir duygusal ve anlatı gerçekliği haline geldiğini araştırıyor.

Tezin ana argümanı, Jean Baudrillard'ın teorileştirdiği hipergerçeklik kavramsal çerçevesi üzerinden geliştirilmiştir. Bu çalışma, fan kurguyu türev veya altkültürel bir olgu olarak görmek yerine, tekrarlama, topluluk konsensüsü ve duygusal tutarlılık yoluyla üretilen simüle edilmiş gerçeklerin orijinal metnin otoritesinin yerini aldığı bir alan olarak ele almaktadır. Yazarlar, alternatif evren fan kurgularında (AU) bile duygusal tutarlılığın korunması ve karakterlerin motivasyonlarının anlatımsal olarak gerekçelendirilmesi gerektiğini defalarca vurgulamaktadır. Marvel ve Harry Potter gibi mega hayran topluluklarında, bu fanon yapıları zaman zaman kanondan daha gerçek hale gelir; bazı topluluklar tarafından referans alınır, tartışılır ve duygusal olarak yaşanır.

Araştırma ayrıca, üretkenlik, trope seçimi, zamanlama ve topluluk katılımı yoluyla kültürel sermayenin hayran topluluğu içinde nasıl işlediğini de ele almaktadır. Dahası, tez fan kurguyu duygusal ve politik bir direniş biçimi olarak konumlandırır: alternatif ilişkiler, queer kimlikler ve duygusal gerçeklerin kolektif hikaye anlatımı uygulamalarıyla ön plana çıktığı bir alan.

Sonuç olarak, bu çalışma fan kurguyu, okuyucuların ve yazarların işbirliği içinde hipergerçek bir sembolik düzen oluşturdukları, anlatı meşruiyetinin artık yazarlığa değil, duygusal rezonansa ve kolektif simülasyona dayandığı söylemsel ve duygusal bir alan olarak ortaya koyar.

INTRODUCTION

“Many people attend concerts, collect recordings, enjoy the cinema and watch television. Almost everyone loves a particular star or TV show. Whether the fascination is with Sting or Spiderman, Marilyn or Twilight, almost everyone self-identifies as a fan in some sense¹”

Mark Duffett - Understanding Fandom (2013)

Branching from culture and media studies, fan studies reveals how popular culture has shifted from a one-way broadcast system into a participatory economy in which audiences actively rewrite, remix, and monetise the very texts that once positioned them as passive consumers (Jenkins, 1992). Understanding fandom is essential for grasping how identity, community, and symbolic value are now produced outside traditional cultural industries.

Scholars started Fandom research in late 1980s, when John Fiske (1989) redefined television audiences as *productive consumers* and argued that popular culture acquires meaning through what viewers do with it. The discussions and academic interest to fandoms came as a question and answer to its time. Cultural studies were expanding, home technologies such as the VCR and word processors became affordable, and most crucially early networked spaces made fan labour suddenly visible. *Star Trek* fans, for example, were already swapping episode scripts over ARPANET mailing lists by 1976; in 1982 they founded net.startrek, one of Usenet’s first dedicated forums, whose traffic soon demanded its own sub-hierarchy. Building on this newly accessible corpus of fan practice, Henry Jenkins’s *Textual Poachers* (1992) offered a landmark ethnography coining the term of “textual poaching” to describe how readers appropriate and re-author mass-media narratives in order to carve out spaces of identity, pleasure, and community. Jenkins linked these creative appropriations to earlier folk traditions, thereby reframing fans not as media dupes but as vernacular cultural producers whose labour troubles copyright regimes and authorial hierarchies.

Ethnographers Camille Bacon-Smith (1992) and Constance Penley (1997) uncovered the largely female, affect-driven worlds of fan-fiction circles. Drawing on participant observation and narrative analysis, Bacon-Smith documented how slash (romance fanfictions)

¹ Mark DUFFETT (2013). Understanding Fandom, Bloomsbury Publishing, p.23

writers used speculative romance between male characters to negotiate gender, sexuality, and care work; whereas Penley combined feminist film theory with psychoanalysis to argue that women's fan writing both critiques and re-scripts patriarchal media texts. Together, their work foregrounded gender politics as a central component of fan practice. Matt Hills (2002) theorised fandom as a performed blend of affect, expertise, and cultural capital. Finally, Mark Duffett's *Understanding Fandom* (2013) mapped the field's interdisciplinary reach and crystallised *fan studies* as a distinct research agenda devoted to examining how fans negotiate power, create value, and build community through media.

Fandom now threads itself through the ordinary rhythms of everyday life: phones ping with chapter-drop alerts at dawn, playlists named after favourite "ships" soundtrack commutes, and weekend plans revolve around global watch-along streams. This ubiquity makes fandom a revealing mirror of late-capitalist society. It is far more than recreational trivia; it is a strategic vantage point from which to observe how culture, labour, and power now intersect. In a digitised service economy, individuals increasingly anchor their self-narratives to media texts (Duffett, 2013).

Empirical work confirms the depth of that identification: Bennett (2013) finds that daily participation in fan forums predicts stronger senses of belonging than many offline civic groups, while Obst et al. (2002) map fan conventions onto McMillan & Chavis's four pillars of community (membership, influence, shared emotional connection, needs fulfilment). Fandom also exposes the cultural field's hidden labour relations; unpaid tagging, beta-reading, and playlist-curation generate fresh value streams for platforms, buttressing a "gift economy" that paradoxically feeds corporate profits (Busse, 2015). Black's longitudinal studies (2007; 2009) trace how writers translate that volunteer labour into professional trajectories, converting what begins as hobby into career capital.

Analysing fandom therefore yields dividends on multiple fronts: it clarifies the micro-mechanics of identity construction; it uncovers how community forms under platform capitalism; it surfaces the unpaid labours scaffolding billion-dollar IP; and it renders visible the contestation of power in real time, as fans negotiate authorship, ownership, and representation. For scholars of sociology, culture, and media industries alike, ignoring fandom would mean overlooking one of the most dynamic arenas in which twenty-first-century social life is being composed, contested, and lived.

A brief survey of existing scholarship reveals two dominant emphases. The first centres on how fandoms form and sustain a “sense of community,” charting participatory dynamics and affective bonds (Jenkins 1992; Bennett 2013; Obst et al. 2002). The second treats fan-fiction primarily as romantic text authored by women, probing questions of gender, desire, and textual subversion (Bacon-Smith 1992; Penley 1997; Black 2007; Busse 2015). What remains under-explored is the sociological impact of fan-fiction on collective perception and how these rewritings reshape the way fans understand canon, identity, and representation, and, crucially, which writer profiles are driving that transformation. By constructing a typology of fan-fiction authors and analysing the perceptual shifts their works generate, this thesis seeks to fill that gap, offering a producer-centred contribution to fan studies and an empirical case for cultural sociology.

In his book, Duffett makes the distinction between fandom research and fan studies like this:

“Fandom research is a very broad, long-standing, multi-disciplinary body of scholarship that takes fandom as its primary focus. ... Fan studies is a much narrower area which has emerged from cultural studies in the last two decades. Its practitioners aim to represent fandom in a positive light and tend to study fan communities and practices²”.

In this research we will focus on fanfiction with a fan studies lens, and aim to see how it operates as a space where cultural norms are rewritten, communities are built, and hyperreal narratives thrive. To make an analysis, we examine three core pillars: a fanfiction text, a couple accepted fanon versions of certain characters, and a field work focusing on fanfiction writers.

We, firstly, focus on a Harry Potter fanfiction called All the Young Dudes. This (almost) 530 thousand word fanfiction has more than 17 million hits and earned its own fandom. So now that there are people who identify as ATYD fans rather than Harry Potter fans, and the fanfic’s original characters have their very own fanfictions. This work, we believe, is important to show how a fan-generated narrative can attain canonical status within its own community, thus embodying Baudrillard’s notion of hyperreality and Bourdieu’s ideas on cultural capital. Alongside this, we focus on Avengers Tower fanfics where the fandom collectively agrees on certain behaviours of Avengers members while they have their domestic life and though this fandom transforms the space in narrative, then we focus on the

² Mark DUFFET (2013). Understanding Fandom, Bloomsbury Publishing, p.24

trans-Viktor fanfictions. These are the stories that reimagine Viktor from the Arcane tv show as a transgender character. These fics often serve as counter-discourses, reframing Viktor's narrative of chronic illness, bodily transformation, and isolation through a trans lens. By doing so, they open space for marginalized identities to be seen and understood, allowing trans writers and readers to find resonance and agency in reinterpreting a character whose canonical arc already grapples with questions of physical and moral transformation. Finally, through a typology of fanfiction writers, we aim to explore the diverse motivations and social roles of those who create these narratives. Drawing on Foucault's "author-function" and Bourdieu's field theory, this typology allows for a sociologically grounded understanding of who writes fanfiction, why they do so, and how their labour reshapes notions of authorship and legitimacy of fanon narratives, thus create fanon as an accepted hyperreality. Together, these three focal points aim to construct a holistic picture of fanfiction not as a marginal or escapist activity, but as a dynamic, politically meaningful cultural practice.

CHAPITRE I - Fan Production, Participatory Culture, and the Order Constructed in the Reality of New Media: A Conceptual Framework

Today, fanfiction is much more than just a fun pastime or a show of admiration. As the internet became a third space (Black, 2007); fandoms have become an area of creative production, identity negotiation, and resistance to cultural norms. Online fan communities, which began to form in the 1980s, born from love of media (Jenkins, 1992), of television and cinema in particular, have transformed into a global production area with the spread of the web, first through blogs and forums, then through social media and digital archives.

This digitization has made it easier for fans to share their output not only as consumers but also as producers; it has created a space that goes beyond the original - canonical text through practices such as storytelling, character development, and even universe expansion. The theoretical basis of this transformation was first laid by Henry Jenkins and then discussed more by critics such as Matthew Hills.

I. Foundations of Participatory Culture: Jenkins and Hills

One of the main works which helped fan studies become pivotal is the 1992 book *Textual Poachers* by Henry Jenkins. Inspired by Michel de Certeau's "poaching" metaphor, Jenkins redefined it not as a mere theft of the meaning from the original text but as an act of creative rewriting. For de Certeau, poaching is a form of everyday resistance by ordinary individuals against dominant narratives. Jenkins applied this framework to fandom, repositioning fans from passive consumers to active cultural producers.

According to Jenkins, fans do not merely consume the original texts; they write about them, discuss them, transform them and produce a collective meaning. This production is at the centre of what Jenkins calls "participatory culture". This approach offers an important alternative to the approaches who saw the media as a centralised broadcasting system at the time. Jenkins' model allows us to think of fandom not only as a matter of 'entertainment' but also as a form of 'public space'.

However, in *Fan Cultures* (2002), Matthew Hills, who takes a more critical perspective against Jenkins' 'heroising' approach to fans, argues that fandom is rather a field full of contradictions, where belonging and performance are intertwined. Hills' major contribution is that he sees fan identity as a performative and contextualised form rather than a fixed one. Unlike Jenkins, Hills emphasises that fandom is shaped by the production of cultural capital and hierarchies established from within and without. Pierre Bourdieu's concept of "cultural capital" becomes important here.

According to Hills, some fans have more prestige than others: practices such as writing with better grammar, getting more likes, using beta readers, or writing "meta" make them more prestigious. This allows us to understand how authorial legitimacy is also produced in fanfiction. Thus, fans, who Jenkins sees as "equal producers", become actors surrounded by internal hierarchies and in Hills' framework.

II. Authorship, Legitimacy and Economies of Prestige in Fanfiction

Unlike the classic image of a writer, alone in their study and writing; fanfiction writers write within dynamic, interconnected communities. Their creative practice is not merely personal, it is inherently social and political, tied to ongoing negotiations over visibility, legitimacy, and cultural authority in digital spaces. Being an "author" is a discursive position, as Foucault states; and this position is constructed both individually and collectively in the field of fanfiction.

In her book Fathallah analyses how fanfiction operates in the context of "author-function". She answers Foucault's classic question "Who can speak?" within fandom as follows: anyone can write, but not everyone is considered an 'author'. Some people's writings are reblogged, commented on, and stand out in archives because they conform to certain literary and social codes. Fathallah considers this invisible hierarchy of fandom together with

Bourdieu's concept of cultural capital. Factors such as writing style, archiving knowledge, correct use of labels, "meta" writings within fandom are factors that increase the authority of the author.

Kristina Busse is another important figure who develops this observation. In her article *Fan Labour and Feminism*, Busse argues that not only production, but also commenting, editing (*beta reading*), writing manifestos or analyses provide a form of cultural capital. In our observation especially platforms such as AO3 and Tumblr make such contributions more visible, creating prestigious fan-writing models. Busse argues that fan communities are structured by a neoliberal understanding of freedom. On the surface, authorship is voluntary no one is paid, no one is obligated to produce. But in reality, success depends on visibility, recognition, and competitive engagement. She reveals that even unpaid creative spaces are not free from structural power.

Hills elaborates this hierarchy through a performative identity theory. The fan-writer not only produces content, but also constructs a certain 'persona' within fandom. Hills' concept of "fan-scholars" shows that people with certain theoretical literacy in fandom gain prestige not only through creative but also analytical contributions which he calls 'elite-fans'. In other words, a kind of 'intellectual elite' is formed in fandom. This elite consists of people who analyse, give theoretical references and write texts with high emotional depth. This is an important criticism of Jenkins' romantic vision of 'everyone being a producer'.

The theoretical analyses of these academic figures are empirically supported by Rebecca Black's findings based on field research. Black analyses ESL (English as a second language) youth writing on fanfiction.net. In her research, she shows that writers who follow the rules of grammar and use English as a "native" language receive more likes and comments, whereas writers who make language mistakes are often ignored. Black's findings prove that following 'formal norms' in fanfiction is directly related to prestige. In other words, it is not only necessary to tell a good story, but also to tell it correctly.

In the following part we'll talk about slash (in the simplest terms romance) stories. However in the context of fanfic-writer's prestige, Wood's *Straight Women, Queer Texts* is an important study. She shows that prestige is established not only through formal but also through identity boundaries. Wood discusses the ethical criticisms that heterosexual women face when writing "slash fiction" about male-male relationships. Such writers are accused of "exploiting" the experiences of queer individuals. Prestige here depends not only on the

quality of the writing, but also on whether we identify with the queer community. In other words, 'authorised authorship' depends not only on technical competence but also on political position.

Each fan studies article or book one way or another takes Pierre Bourdieu's work on socio-cultural capital as its theoretical grounding, and make analyses with the help of concepts of field and habitus. In our observations formed from being lifelong fans, it is clear that each fandom has its own rules, it is truly hard to make a sociological typology for fans or fandoms in general. Also being in a certain fandom doesn't necessarily mean each sub-groups, communities in it has the same moral codes, perceptions of the characters or reading preferences. Fanfiction is an autonomous field with its own rules, value systems, norms and prestige codes. In order to exist in this field, it is necessary to have certain habitus, that is, to be able to "feel" the rules of that field. Therefore, Jenkins' participatory culture approach, in which "everyone is equally productive", becomes open to criticism in this context. Everyone can produce, but not everyone is visible in the same way.

III. Neoliberalism, Fan Labour and Commercialisation of Media

Fan production by its own very nature is always free. They are the re-imaginings of already told stories. Since fanfiction authors produce content based on copyrighted characters and universes, they cannot directly earn financial income from these stories. Still, in some forms of fandom production (e.g. fanart-character drawings) this limit is more flexible, the artist can set up donation links (e.g. ko-fi, Patreon) or offer commissioned art. However, our experience shows that this is not the case for fanfiction authors. Fanfiction is both in a greyer area in terms of copyright and culturally more tightly woven with the norms of the 'gift economy'. Writing is in a "gift culture" based on volunteerism, unpaid labour and mutual emotional investment.

Busse (2015) explains fan labour in terms of "invisible labour". The fanfiction writer produces texts, offers them to readers for free, acts as a beta reader, writes commodities, organises events but all this production is never recognised as "work". According to Busse, this is masked by the neoliberal discourse of "freedom, creativity, community". However, the limits of this voluntary labour have long been overstepped: today, many companies either directly copy the content that fans produce for free or produce content using their language

and aesthetics. She talks about marketing brands who “*Learn how brands can use UGC [user-generated content] to drive unprecedented ROI.*” The main thing here is to manipulate the emotional attachment of fans to make them feel like they 'belong' to the brand. By imitating the ironic or emotional editing aesthetics of fans, brands both create a viral effect and extract copyrighted content from fan labour.

Dan Schiller offers a more structural analysis of this structure in his work *Transmedia Storytelling*. According to him, the media industry no longer just produces content; it outsources production to external sources, namely the fans. This strategy not only means "turning the customer into a content producer", but also placing the production risk, marketing costs, and viral effects on the fan. Schiller's neoliberal media strategy is about production appearing decentralized and "free" but remaining completely centralized and controlled.

Today, the concrete equivalent of this strategy is the TikTok edit culture and memes. The virality of a new TV series or film often starts with 30-60 second of these fan edits. Those who make these edits are usually teenage individuals (in our observation usually female). If there is a popular ship there are edits of it with Taylor Swift in the background. If a teenager somewhere liked a TV show, you can be sure they'll make a 30 second edit watched by millions. When these videos go viral, they got shared and pick interest of common people. People who have no previous intent, start to watch the show, and among these people some of them became fans. And these fans buy merch, attend events, algorithmically move the tv show up. The editors who start this cycle receive no economic reward.

These examples illustrate one of the mechanism of neoliberalism: the commodification of production through the exploitation of emotion. Ahmed's (2004) theorisation of the political nature of emotions becomes important here. Every emotion written in fanfiction can turn into a measurable KPI for companies: likes, comments, shares, interaction. Emotions become data for capital.

IV. Canon is Dead, Long Live Fanon: Baudrillard, Simulacrum and Hyperreality

The canon story may be an amazing piece of science fiction, a high school drama, a 'cringe' YA novel; for the fandom this is not important. Fans start their discourse not from the

story's but the characters' perspectives. Would Sirius Black like David Bowie, what is Steve Rogers' favourite cupcake or is Viktor from Arcane a trans man?

In these discourses fans came up with *headcanons*, the little Truths that they came up with. After years and with thousands if not millions of fans contributions they became *fanons*, fandom's canon.

Fanfiction is not only rewriting of a text; it is also transcending the text, establishing a new reality and what fascinating is fans construct this new reality collectively. This situation overlaps strikingly with Jean Baudrillard's theory of *simulacra*. Baudrillard argues that in contemporary societies, the boundaries between reality and representation are erased and eventually transformed into simulacra, representations that replace reality. Fanfiction is precisely one of the areas where this "transcendence of reality" is embodied: fanons are created, characters are rewritten, emotional histories are reshaped, and eventually this alternative reality overrides the original text.

Baudrillard's simulacrum theory proposes a four-stage process of representation. There are now, according to him, copies of copies of copies. At the final stage, the final copy, ctd. a simulation, has no longer has anything to do with reality.

In fandom's context, of course not every fanfiction or character reaches that. However especially in mega fandoms (Jamison, 2013) where the discourse happens by millions over the years, we see this transformation from the canon. The text we'll study in Chapter II, a fanfiction called *All the Young Dudes* (ATYD) is a prime example of this final stage.

Similarly, the example of Trans Viktor (Arcane) presents an important simulacrum process in terms of rewriting queer representations. The character Viktor, who is not explicitly mentioned in the canon as queer nor trans but reshaped by fan interpretations. In the fandom he is accepted as a trans man. This is not just a representational gesture; it is a space of belonging for trans writers and readers. Here, fanfiction breaks normative gender narratives and reconstructs the character's body, past and desires. The simulation is so powerful that for some fans "Viktor = trans" becomes an unquestionable reality. This is the formation of queer hyperreality: non-canon but more meaningful, unofficial but more "real".

Baudrillard's theory is not limited to grand narratives. The simulacrum effect can also be seen in details like Thor's love of Pop-Tarts. Although this feature is only mentioned as a joke in canon, it becomes one of the main identity traits of the character in fan production. In

fanon, a brief detail in the original text becomes the character's most beloved feature, an integral part of his identity. This transformation shows that the "true" nature of the character is rewritten by the fans.

This stage of simulacrum is a universe where not only narrative but also social identity, affect and moral values are reconstructed. Fanfiction creates alternative social orders here. Queer love is not lost, characters are not killed just to create a "shock effect", individual traumas are met with collective healing. In other words, fanfiction is not only a textual but also an ethical, emotional and political rewriting.

In this context, fanfiction is both a form of creativity against the textual constraints of capitalist media production and an endeavour to produce meaning in postmodern society. Narratives of collective mourning as in *ATYD*, identity struggles as in the case of Trans Viktor, and symbols such as Pop-Tart Thor show how fanfiction creates a space of hyperreality, both personal and cultural. These simulacra do not replace reality; they transcend it, transform it, and often evolve into a more "real" version of it.

V. Affect, Queerness and the Textualization of Desire in Fanfiction

One of the most, if not the most, popular fanfiction stories are slash stories. In the simplest term these are romance stories. Fandoms form around the love of the characters. Like we explained in the last part, they rewrite and deepen the characters. In fanfiction, fans tend to write these characters not going on adventures but build the story around the romantic relationships of characters. In each fandom there are several ships (romantic pairs), for example Marvel fans tend to write about Steve Rogers/Tony Stark, Steve Rogers/Bucky Barnes etc. These characters are usually men. The interesting part is that this male-male romance stories are usually written by women.

In her qualitative research on *Ranma ½ Fanfiction*, Carolyn Michelle Aquila argues that fanfiction writing is not only a form of creation for individuals, but also a site of identification, identity construction and emotional expression. Aquila removes fanfiction from

narrow definitions such as "self-insertion"³ and instead positions this act of writing as a tool for understanding and defining one's internal identity processes.

Her interviews reveal that many female readers do not care about characters' gender, but instead focus on their personality, emotional vulnerability, and capacity for growth. This explains why many women are drawn to slash fiction, they're seeking stories with intimacy, growth, and emotional stakes.

A key theme in Aquila's analysis is the appeal of the *enemies-to-lovers trope*. Rivalries, particularly those between two male characters, offer a stage where power is distributed equally. In contrast to traditional heterosexual romances, which often embed patriarchal dynamics of dominance and submission, slash fiction involving adversarial male pairings (such as Draco/Harry or Spock/Kirk) presents a more symmetrical relational structure. This symmetry allows readers to explore vulnerability, care, and intimacy without the trappings of gendered social roles. For many readers, this structure creates what Aquila describes as an "equal ground" a space where both characters can be emotionally open, fragile, and transformed through love.

Crucially, Aquila notes that many women who read and write slash do not identify with the characters as objects of desire, but instead through them, often using male characters as vehicles for expressing their own suppressed or marginalized emotions. The identification is affective and narrative-driven rather than rooted in sexuality or gender expression. In this light, slash fiction functions not as fetishization, but as a site of emotional authenticity, allowing writers and readers to explore tenderness, trauma, and reconciliation in ways mainstream media rarely permits, especially for women and queer audiences. For Aquila's participants, slash fiction becomes a form of emotional realism: a means of imagining relationships where vulnerability is not gendered, and where emotional connection is not constrained by heteronormative formulas. Through this lens, fanfiction emerges not simply as derivative or playful text, but as a deeply personal and political medium for exploring affect, desire, and relational ethics. In our opinion, dismissing slash stories as merely love stories is as reductive as dismissing Jane Austen's stories as merely love stories.

Sara Ahmed's theoretical framework *Queer Feelings* is quite functional to explain this affective aspect. Ahmed states that emotions are shaped around objects and orientations, not

³ the creation of a character that resembles the author, stories where it's obvious that author writes romance imagining themselves

between individuals. According to Ahmed, emotions are navigable, culturally codifiable and spatializable structures. In this sense, fanfiction creates a space where emotions are directed towards "wrong" texts and desire deviates from normative routes. Slash stories suggest not only the absence of heterosexual love, but also ways out of masculine violence, militarism and toxic masculinity. Through this emotional reorientation, fanfiction constructs a kind of queer heterotopia: an alternative, non-normative but familiar universe.

Fandom is not only a form of consumption, but also a mythological and melodramatic commitment (Duffett, 2013). In particular, stories organised around themes of loss, bereavement and trauma become emotional centres that trigger the production of fanfiction. In this respect, stories such as *All The Young Dudes* (ATYD) are not only alternative narratives; they are also a collective space of mourning, a process of creating an emotional community. In Duffett's approach, melodrama is not a weakness or an escape, but a strategy for creating connection and collective meaning-making.

We should also point out that fanfiction does not only offer alternative love narratives. These stories often contain multi-layered analyses of the psychological depth, historical background and social class positions of the characters. In this sense, Slash functions as a kind of "alternative character study". For example, the character Steve Rogers of Marvel Comics, not only a hero with superpowers; he is also "Captain *America*" - representing a national ideal, a hegemonic order and a normative masculinity. He actually reproduces the core values of neoliberal society: the preservation of order, the maintenance of the status quo, the unifying figure of power against threats. From this perspective, superheroes do not save the world; they save the order, the norm and the nation-state imaginary.

However, this is precisely why fanfiction plays a critical role. Because the details that are left out of the original narrative or mostly ignored, are brought back to the centre through fan production. Canonically Steve Rogers born in 1918 and is coming from a first-generation Irish immigrant family who lives in Brooklyn. None of these traits are paid much attention in MCU or comics. In many fanfictions, where at first look seen as a romance story between Steve Rogers and Tony Stark, historical and cultural details such as Steve Rogers being a character born in 1918, coming from an immigrant family of Irish origin, and having witnessed the aftermaths of New York's gang wars or being a queer person in the 1920s are strongly processed in fanfiction. These rewritings reveal the historical specificity of the

character and transform him from an idealised national hero into a multidimensional subject with traumas, migration history and queer readings.

Fanfiction is thus positioned as a literary genre in which emotions are not only represented but also performed, transgressing norms and enabling new identity positions. Under the guise of romance, narratives such as Slash offer a much deeper sociological transformation: characters are historically reframed, their ethnic or class origins are emphasised, and often the unresolved conflicts presented by the mainstream are reworked with emotional integrity in these alternative narratives.

CHAPITRE II - NARRATIVE PRACTICES OF THE COMMUNITY

As we move from theoretical groundwork to empirical investigation, this chapter offers an intermediary space where key concepts are put into motion. Rather than presenting fan communities as abstracted or homogenous, we turn to three cases that illuminate how fanon operates at the level of narrative, space, and embodiment. These close readings — of *All the Young Dudes*, Avengers Tower fanfictions, and Trans!Viktor fanon — will allow us to trace the textures of collective authorship and affective engagement that will later resurface in our field observations.

I. Analyse de contenu: All the Young Dudes - Simulacra and Sorrow

As of the 1st of June; MsKingBean89's Harry Potter fanfiction "All the Young Dudes"⁴ which has been released on the most popular fanfic platform Archive of Our Own, has almost 18 million hits and 267 thousand kudos.

To put it on a scale; New York Times criteria for New York Times Best Sellers is a novel that sells from 1,000 to 10,000 copies per week. The majority of New York Times bestselling books sell from 10,000 to 100,000 copies in their first-year. *All the Young Dudes* finished in November 2018.

18 million hits in six and a half years.

This massive story of 527.000 words, along with its own fan-arts, fan-videos, edits, and own inner jokes deserves special attention in fan studies. This section will examine *All the Young Dudes* not merely as a Harry Potter fan narrative but as a hyperreal locus of collective emotion, canon subversion, and identity-work. We argue that the work's extraordinary popularity lies in the way it channels melodrama, queer memory, and participatory authorship into a digital commons that enables readers to negotiate feelings and identities that hegemonic media leave unarticulated. The discussion ties directly to the conceptual frame outlined in Chapter I.

⁴ <https://archiveofourown.org/works/10057010/chapters/22409387> (01.06.2025)

Many of the videos that one can find on TikTok are crying videos of young women caused by the sorrowful ending of ATYD (All the Young Dudes). At the end of the 30s, melodrama, marketed specifically to women which led women to go to the cinemas in groups, and that collective crying in these melodramas was strikingly similar to hysteria (Nowell-Smith, 1977). This catharsis, produced by a bodily symptom, pushed us to see if we can create a resemblance between the reactions to stories of melodrama and angst, and if we can find a reason for that.

Both fandoms (Jamison, 2013) and Dungeons & Dragons (Adams, 2013) communities / games encourage creativeness and create a safe place to participate. The lack of third spaces and communities in our post-modern world; these fantasy lands help fans to create a community, have interactions and most importantly like all science fiction at its core give the participant a support for the daily life (Karmen, 2013).

Fandoms have been around for a long time (Jamison, 2013); the first fandom community that we can name goes back to the late 19th century with Sherlock Holmes. The housewives of London created a mailing network and shared their ideas for the future stories, discussed theories, and yes wrote fanfiction. In the post-modern world, the first fandom that we can accept where a group of people connect through the internet who collectively discuss, analyse, criticize and get obsessed over it; who create content for an already hungry community, who already want to read them, who want to talk about them, and who may be writing about them too is Star Trek. While nowadays Star Trek fandom has both men and women fans, it also began within housewives.

The similarities between Sherlock Holmes fandom and Star Trek fandom are important for our thesis, since both emerged within housewives in the industrial capitals of the world, but most importantly they exist because of their times' technology. For Sherlock fans in the 1890s the invention of the mimeograph has become the engine of fan writing publication and distribution for decades. The Star Trek fandom became the first modern fic-writing group in the 80s when the internet became a thing.

Currently, the most popular fanfiction web site is Archive of Our Own. As of 14 May 2025, Archive of Our Own hosts over 15,000,000 works in over 71,720 fandoms⁵. In this vast

⁵ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250101114910/https://archiveofourown.org/> (01.06.2025)

sea of story types, anything you want to read and don't want to read can be filtered. Ao3 lets you include or exclude whichever *trops* you wish.

Trops are the main / stereotypical storylines. For example; a story where Iron Man is a baker and meets Captain America in his coffee shop is simply called a 'Coffee Shop AU (*Alternate-Universe*)'. One of the most popular trope in each and every one of fandoms is called '*Angst*'⁶.

Angst originated from German and translates to 'fear' and 'anxiety', which means a feeling of great worry about a situation, or about your life⁷. In fanfic, it means not only a character experiencing anxiety or fear but also heartbreak, physical or emotional pain, and abuse... overall in general; the character is in a disturbing setting. There is no general rule of angst about its ending. We've come across an equal amount of bad and good endings. But almost every fanfic, if not all, has 'warning tags' at the beginning of the story, such as: Hurt, Hurt/Comfort, Hurt/No Comfort, Angst, Angst with a happy ending, Angst with a sad ending etc.

Why collectively many women or queer people read this sorrowful stories?

We think it's the very same reason why women of the 30s collectively went to melodramas to cry their eyes out: to bodily feel a catharsis that isn't welcomed in this 'rational' world.

i. About 'All the Young Dudes'

Marauders are the mischievous friend group of Harry Potter's father; James Potter, Sirius Black, Remus Lupin and Peter Pettigrew. All we know about these characters is, in canon, despite the entire team being best friends, James and Sirius are like brothers, but because of Peter's betrayal, James and his wife Lily are killed by Voldemort, however Sirius is blamed and is convicted for the death of James, Lily and Peter, and thrown into prison. Remus, the last remaining member of the team, leads a miserable life for 12 years; until Sirius Black escapes from prison and Remus begins teaching at Hogwarts in the third book.

⁶ <https://archiveofourown.org/tags> (01.06.2025)

⁷ <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/angst?q=angst> (02.06.2022)

The only divergence of All the Young Dudes from canon is Remus Lupin's father is dead and Remus was raised in a children's home. Oh and Remus Lupin and Sirius Black are in a romantic queer relationship which in fandom is called: Wolfstar.

Over the course of 188 chapters, the story follows the slowly growing relationship between Remus and Sirius as well as the lives of James and Peter and Lily; the gang from their very first year at Hogwarts to the end of Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban, a 27 year span of time. The story is told from the perspective of Remus who as being a werewolf and a gay man in the 70s, has to hide a piece of his identity both from the wizarding world and muggle society. Even the story's name comes from "All the Young Dudes" by Mott the Hoople. The song was originally written by David Bowie in 1972 and became one of the earliest gay anthems to top the charts⁸.

There are also a lot of class discrimination statements; growing up in a children's home Remus is always aware of his socio-economic place. He spends his summers in a children's home and when school starts he packs up his bag to go to his fancy elite school. And like an immigrant he is aware that he doesn't belong either. Towards the end, after finishing school, he and Sirius move to the muggle London when Margaret Thatcher was the prime minister.

Throughout the whole story, at moments when we think the story is going well, things then start to get way worse. Such as; Remus is in a children's home where he is treated terribly and then he starts Hogwarts but he doesn't have anyone, he starts to be friends with the boys but he is still a werewolf, during their adolescence his relationship with Sirius starts to peak and then Sirius does something horrible (which is one of the bottom pits of the story) etc. And of course, the big bad end; they finish school, move to London, their best friends have a kid and then, Remus loses everything.

The author says from the very beginning that they won't change the ending, so it's going to end as canon: both Sirius and Remus's deaths in combat. Even though we as the audience of Harry Potter know that they will die horribly at the end, even though the author says they won't change the outcome, they write the ending as; Remus and Sirius embracing each other in their home, warm and safe, just before their inevitable ends.

⁸ MIA SWARTZ (2022). The Color Code: Messages in Music Regarding Social Marginality « LGBTQ+ Representation in Music from the 1970s to Today », <https://wordpress.clarku.edu/musc099-04/all-the-young-dudes-by-mott-the-hoople/> (01.06.2025)

ii. The Fandom of All the Young Dudes (not Harry Potter)

After the release of the third film in 2004, Marauders started to grow their own fandom. However, there were not enough materials in canon for the characters or info about their own time in Hogwarts. This is how fandoms rise, they emerge when the canon isn't enough (Jenkins, 2013). In various fandom platforms and Tumblr fans started to write head-cansons, fanfics, arts... Thousands of people, if not millions have put pieces to these characters for years. Now, it is generally accepted that; Sirius Black has tattoos, smokes, and wears a leather jacket; Remus Lupin loves chocolate, and comes with all master pranks but doesn't get in trouble because he looks like a quiet, decent student. What happened to Sirius and Remus is the very same thing as what happened to Achilles. Maybe we are not telling the story of Marauders for three thousand years but we've been telling their stories for the last 25 years *on the internet*. Baudrillard's *simulacrum* becomes visible when ATYD's details eclipse Rowling's text in everyday fan knowledge.

This is the point where we call 'the death of the Author' (Walter, XXX). Baudrillard calls it 'hyperrealism', as a result of post-modern culture, the blurring of the lines between what is real and what is simulated from reality. If you ask a random person if Achilles ever got shot from his heel, they'll say yes; just like if you ask a Marauders fan if Sirius' full name is Sirius Orion Black. But you'll find out that none of these facts were ever canon in their main stories.

Almost at the end of each chapter, the author puts 70s rock pieces that Marauders listen to and has historical importance; such as Bowie, T-Rex, The Velvet Underground, Slade, and many more outcasts and queers. You can find a Spotify list of the songs with over 30.000 likes. These artists are not random; 'gender benders' such as Bowie played with the idea of gender and its strict definitions; when people were looking for an identity, they became gender models (Baudrillard, 1989).

The story really had its peak during the second year of the pandemic, around the winter of 2020. This population came from TikTok, more precisely, fanfiction TikTok. In November 2020 ATYD had just under 300,000 hits, by the end of January 2021, 3 months later the story had reached just under a million hits⁹. One and a half years later it had 7 million hits, now almost 18 million.

⁹ Rachele HAMPTON (2021). "The Best Harry Potter Novel Isn't Written by J.K. Rowling", <https://slate.com/culture/2021/11/all-the-young-dudes-harry-potter-fanfic-wolfstar-tiktok.html> (12.06.2022)

When we were making a previous research in 2022, TikTok ‘all the young dudes’ tag had more than 413 million views of fanarts, printed book covers, cosplays, reactions, film-like edits, jokes – memes; ‘atyd’ tag had 1.1 billion, ‘atydtiktok’ tag has 79.2 million views. The story now has translated into 53 languages (again by fans).

Remember the reasons why Sherlock Holmes and Star Trek were able to create a community: technology.

“All the Young Dudes” got this popular because it had the perfect timing. Not only it had the platform to rise, it's a story set during Thatcher's presidency, but meanwhile, in real life, there was Donald Trump in America and Boris Johnson in the UK, the pandemic pushed people to seek comfort from real life. Science-fictional or fantastic spaces become therapeutic third places when offline community structures erode (Karmen, 2013). Last but not least, as always, in male-dominated mainstream media women and queer people were in lack of stories.

Which brings us to our next topic; stories for women.

iii. Melodrama to Angst

Melodrama originally meant drama and music (*melos*) (Nowell-Smith, 1977). This 18th-century sense survives grand opera, becomes the most popular form of American theatre (Dormon, 1969) and finally became an essential genre for cinema (Adanır, 2021).

Melodrama is differentiated from tragedy firstly by its ending; unlike tragedy, the first melodrama stories usually had a happy ending, secondly, instead of heroes of grand myths, characters of melodramas were bourgeois (Nowell-Smith, 1977). The genre changed with its time and its audience. And now melodrama evolved into angst and the audience is, instead of solemnly women, everyone who can't find their representations or who isn't satisfied with the mass media.

Nowell-Smith suggests that in melodramas, with the help of music, the increased emotional element causes a bodily symptom that is strikingly similar to hysteria. Especially what Freud calls as ‘conversion hysteria’ where the energy attached to a repressed idea returns.

He further explains; that the moments where realistic representation breaks down are moments of catharsis and usually involve all the characters. We see the same themes in angsts; The most devastating moment of ATYD is the part where Remus is left alone after the death of James and Lily and the imprisonment of Sirius. Maybe we can't use *mise-en-scène* in the story, but towards the end of the story - with the narrator's reminders – like in a tragedia, as we are reminded again and again that they really won't have a happy ending; in that moment of realization, that's when you have a hysteria.

Melodrama, even though it seems like it ends in a different place, turns back to a similar situation at the beginning. In this retro respect, melodrama appears linked to time and space. The hysteric suffers from reminiscences (Modleski, 1984). The call back to the past, without an exception, was in each angst story we've ever read.

Different from both tragedy and melodrama, angst stories start in a bad place, whether it's a linear story or with flashbacks. Because it hits when you read a scene where the character is miserable, both of your hearts are broken and then the character remembers a happy memory; that's when you start to cry, after realizing how much they've lost.

The reader starts to grieve with the protagonist. Even though they are alone, the fanfic reader is not; the fan has a community, a fandom, many people who are in the same mental situation as them. The fanfic reader can talk about how sad it is in the comments, in blogs, on Discord or can shoot a video while crying and upload it to TikTok. That's what many fans did with *All the Young Dudes*.

Hills (2002) insists that fans inhabit rather than passively watch emotional narratives; Duffett (2013) describes fandom as a "performance of affective excess". These insights illuminate why queer readers and young women gather online to mourn fictional losses: the communal performance of sorrow both validates private feelings and forges social bonds.

Ehrenberg suggests that; mourning is a collective language which creates 'empathy', a key social value for equality and impersonal relations (Marks, 2021). It has a contemporary importance since with modernism, individuals must create their own identity, this causes a rise in symptoms of inner emptiness and a perception of a loss of connection from the others. The way individual creates social connections turns into a performance in which individual expresses their inner life. Ehrenberg sees the wave of 'la souffrance' in the 90s as a new social language to define our problems (Johnsen, 2011), a way of giving meaning to our lives (Marks, 2021).

During that time Ehrenberg looks at TV and sees it as an accessible popular therapy which provides « a therapeutic guidance in a moment of confusion». It's not that different to expect the same from angst fanfics. At the end of the 19th century, even though Grimstad calls them the most banal stories, he points out that melodramas offer the comfort of divine guidance (Dormon, 1969).

iv. Conclusion – Fanon as Hyperreal Cultural Capital

All the Young Dudes illuminates three interlocking dynamics at the core of contemporary participatory culture. First, through sustained textual poaching the Marauders fandom fills Rowling's narrative lacunae, demonstrating how communities appropriate and extend canonical worlds. Second, MsKingBean89's facilitative role exemplifies Foucault's decentralised author-function: narrative authority migrates from the individual writer to a networked readership that edits, annotates, and sanctions meaning. Third, the story's runaway popularity produces a Baudrillardian simulacrum—a version of the Marauders that is experienced as more “real” than its canonical source and circulates with the cultural gravity of an official franchise despite its unofficial status.

This hyperreal standing has tangible consequences. ATYD not only mediates queer remembrance and collective catharsis; it also spawns secondary canons, such as the substantial corpus of fanfics centred on *Grant Chapman* – an original character of the fanfic became extremely beloved by the readers, so now that there are more than 300 fanfictions of Grant Chapman¹⁰. These recursive expansions confirm that once a simulacrum attains affective legitimacy it becomes self-generating: new stories cite fanon, not canon. In Jenkins' terms, fandom here acts as both archive and laboratory, storing communal memory while continually prototyping fresh narrative possibilities.

The scale of engagement, millions of reads, billions of hashtag views, likewise validates Duffett's claim that fandoms manufacture their own systems of prestige and cultural capital. ATYD functions simultaneously as *archive*, *commons*, and *factory*: it preserves affective memory, offers a shared interpretive horizon, and incessantly produces new narrative goods. Consequently, the case demonstrates that fanfiction is not a peripheral pastime but a central

¹⁰ [https://archiveofourown.org/tags/Grant%20Chapman%20\(MsKingBean89\)/works](https://archiveofourown.org/tags/Grant%20Chapman%20(MsKingBean89)/works) (01.06.2025)

mechanism through which neoliberal publics renegotiate identity, authorship, and the very boundaries of the textual real.

II. Fanonised Space and Body

This section examines how fan communities construct affectively stable versions of characters—what we might call fanonised bodies—and how these reconstructions function as emotional truths within hyperreal systems of meaning. The fan body does not result from individual reinterpretation; it is the product of accumulation, repetition, and emotional consensus.

This section argues that the fanonised body is not a distortion of the canon, but a different symbolic layer. In such systems, characters do not belong to the original text, but to the communities that continue to rewrite them. The fanonised body is emotionally legible even when the textual body is not.

i. Avengers Tower

In the realm of Marvel fanfiction, “Avengers Tower” is not merely a building. It is a narrative infrastructure. Though the tower exists canonically in the Marvel Cinematic Universe (MCU), fanfiction transforms it from a corporate headquarters or battle staging ground into a site of shared domesticity, emotional recovery, and gentle routine. It becomes a fantasy of communal healing, where the traumas of canonical storylines are reworked into rituals of intimacy.

What distinguishes this trope is its collective coherence. Across thousands of unrelated fanfics, the same micro-behaviors reappear: Clint Barton travels in the vents, Bruce Banner brews herbal tea, Tony Stark makes gadgets for each team member, Thor eats pop-tarts. None of these behaviours are sourced from the films or comics. Yet fanwriters replicate them with consistency and intentionality.

These choices are not arbitrary. They emerge from long-standing fandom discourses; Tumblr threads, AO3 comment sections, Discord messages and gradually harden into quasi-canonical truths. New writers entering the fandom often adopt these character traits by default, not as creative inventions but as inherited parameters. This is fanon in its most organic form: authorless, iterative, and collectively legitimized.

This dynamic can be illuminated by the concept of collective intelligence (Jenkins, 2006). Jenkins argued that media audiences pool knowledge across distributed networks rather than relying on centralized authority. In Avengers Tower fanfics, this translates into a distributed archive of character behaviours, emotional registers, and narrative expectations. No single person decides that Clint lives in the vents, but everyone “knows” it. Between fans there is even an expression, a meme if you will, such as: “He wouldn’t fucking say that!”. Fans internalize the way a character speaks and behaves so much that any out-of-character behaviour results in the fanfic being unread and receiving serious criticism. Also many new fans instead of reading comics, reads fanfiction. The first version of the character they met is the fanon version.

The idea is expanded by the argument that fan labor is not restricted to the act of writing (Busse, 2017). Rather, the performance of fandom involves reading, tagging, commenting, and even adhering to established tropes. Writing Clint in the vents is not just a creative act; it’s a social gesture, signalling the writer’s embeddedness in community lore.

In this sense, Avengers Tower is not just a story setting. It is a collective affective architecture. It encodes a shared vision of safety, belonging, and emotional intelligibility. It is both a narrative space and a social contract: by participating in it, writers align themselves with a fandom’s unspoken pact.

This practice also functions as a subtle resistance to the canon’s perpetual violence. In the Marvel Cinematic Universe, characters are constantly thrown into existential crises and battles; fandom, by contrast, reimagines them within routines of healing, softness, and shared domesticity. The tower becomes not a battlefield, but a sanctuary—an anti-canon where trauma is processed through the rhythms of daily life. This aligns with the notion of queer temporality, wherein time unfolds not through grand narrative arcs but through affective recovery (Halberstam, 2005).

Moreover, the repetition of shared character details across stories by unrelated writers illustrates an emergent form of distributed authorship. Jenkins (2006) describes this as a

participatory mode of storytelling where a shared universe is constructed horizontally, rather than by a single authorial voice. Avengers Tower fic is held together not by centralized coordination, but by intertextual cues, fandom memory, and aesthetic consensus.

One of the most powerful instruments of this intertextuality is the tag culture of Archive of Our Own. Phrases like “Tower Fic,” “Domestic Avengers,” or “Everyone Lives in the Tower” are not just categorizations, they are cultural markers. Tags serve as both thematic signals and community shibboleths, allowing readers and writers to navigate a shared imaginary. They mark an entry into a discursive field where emotional familiarity and collective authorship are taken for granted.

Finally, this fanonical transformation of the Tower carries a spatial critique. In canon, Stark Tower is a monument to capitalist futurism. In fanfiction, it is softened and queered. It becomes a communal space with shared kitchens, movie nights, emotional check-ins, and casual softness. Through this transformation, fans enact what Lefebvre (1991) would call the social production of space: reshaping environments of domination into zones of affect and possibility. It encodes a shared vision of safety, belonging, and emotional intelligibility. It is both a narrative space and a social contract: by participating in it, writers align themselves with a fandom’s unspoken pact of care.

ii. Tag Makes the Man - Trans!Viktor

Arcane is a two-season sci-fi animated series set in the universe of *League of Legends*, where class conflict, progress, and survival intertwine. Viktor is introduced as a sickly inventor who immigrated from the polluted undercity of Zaun to so-called top-side, Piltover. As the narrative unfolds, his body begins to change, gets augmented through machines and magic. This combination of geographical migration and medical alteration leaves his gender identity unspoken, providing a poachable void; a space fans can fill with their own meaning (Jenkins, 1992).

With Season 2, Viktor’s body starts to evolve. Fans mapped this evolution onto well-known trans narratives of bodily transition and chosen migration, turning Viktor into an invitation for queer world-building.

On AO3 and Tumblr, the tag “Trans!Viktor” quickly became popular. Tags do more than classify; they perform belonging and mark an epistemic stance within fandom discourse (Busse, 2017). To click or use the tag signals an affective alignment and accrues a form of subcultural capital within the community.

Fic portrayals of Viktor usually has two poles: gentle, domestic transition stories and body-horror explorations of prosthetic change. This duality illustrates fandom’s experimental ethos, using the same character to test both care work and affective risk. Such narratives foreground slow time and everyday negotiation of gender euphoria, aligning with queer temporalities of repair (Halberstam, 2005), while simultaneously opening a sandbox for radical imagination, taboo, and violence.

Because thousands of independent works reiterate trans Viktor, the identity no longer belongs to any single author. The author-function is dissolved into a network of writer–reader interactions (Foucault, 1969). Viktor’s body itself is textually poached, re-gendered through collective intelligence rather than top-down canon. Every new fic citing “Trans!Viktor” strengthens the counter-archive of queer representation (Fathallah, 2017).

The sheer repetition of this portrayal produces a Baudrillardian simulacrum: trans Viktor becomes the Viktor for much of the fandom. His ambiguous canonical body turns into an affective orientation; desire coheres around what is unspoken, enabling a version of Viktor driven more by longing than by origin (Ahmed, 2004; Baudrillard, 1981).

Archive of Our Own provides a stark numeric illustration of this transformation. As of June 2025:

21.204 fanfics include Viktor as main or supporting character.

2.781 of these explicitly tag Viktor as Trans.

Only 397 trans-tagged works were published before Season 2.

In other words, $\approx 85\%$ of all “Trans Viktor” fics emerged after Season 2. Fandom collectively ratified a trans reading in response to new canonical ambiguity. The data confirm that the simulacrum has overtaken the source: the fanon body now governs future fandom storytelling.

iii. From Fanon Worlds to Real-Life Communities

As Kristina Fathallah (2017) argues, fanfiction should not be examined solely through individual texts or authorial intent. Rather, value and legitimacy in fanfiction emerge through the shared labour of writers, readers, taggers, beta readers, and community moderators. In her words, fanfiction is not just a narrative form but a “discursive frame” shaped by “local negotiations of discourse, privilege, and visibility.” This means that fanfiction exists not only as an individual creative product but as a *social practice*, embedded in specific communities and cultural economies.

In Chapter II, we explored how fanon versions of characters emerge and circulate by closely reading widely shared fanfiction works. However, textual analysis alone cannot fully capture how such frames are made, contested, reinforced, or policed in real time. To address this limitation, the next chapter turns to fieldwork. Chapter III focuses on *Marvel Trumps Hate (MTH)*, a semi-organized subcommunity of the Marvel fandom, anchored in a Discord-based writing events and charity auction structure. Within MTH, fanfictions are not only written and shared, but also **commissioned, priced, critiqued, and evaluated** by community members. Writers and readers co-create not only stories, but norms, expectations, and reputational structures that give fanon its symbolic authority.

If Chapter II examined what fanon worlds look like—through narrative tropes, headcanons, and the emotional logic of hyperreality—then Chapter III turns to **how** those worlds are constructed and maintained on the ground. Through interviews and field observation, we will analyze how fanfiction communities negotiate meaning, ethics, visibility, and legitimacy—revealing the discursive infrastructure behind hyperreal storytelling.

CHAPITRE III - RESULTATS SUR LE TERRAIN

RESEARCH AIM AND PARTICIPANT PROFILES

This fieldwork aimed to understand how fanfiction writers relate to fictional worlds, characters, and the communities around them. We wanted to see it through the lens of hyperreality, seeking to understand how a group of people can collectively construct such a strong consensus around certain character versions and how writers as author figures with authority (Fathallah, 2017) actively help to shape and reinforce these parallel realities.

The initial plan was to focus on a specific fan community: Marvel Trumps Hate (MTH). MTH is a large and structured subgroup within the Marvel fandom, centred around the ship Steve/Tony. The group operates a Discord server and regularly organizes several fan events, writing conventions such as Big Bangs (a writing event) and an annual charity auction, where readers donate to selected organizations and writers offer creative works in return¹¹. Though this act does not define the entire Marvel fandom since our work showed that fandoms are segmented entities, MTH constitutes a recognizable subculture characterized by prolific output and a collaborative ethos.

The decision to focus on a specific community was guided by insights from Fathallah (2017), who emphasizes that fan studies should attend not just to individual creators but to the specific fandom microcultures in which they operate. By engaging with writers within a well-defined group like MTH, the goal was to observe how norms, discourses, and interpretive frameworks circulate within a bounded yet participatory environment. And of course we wanted to see if this group of people have the same consensus about the same characters.

Six participants were affiliated with MTH, with 2 interviewees particularly known within the group. Due to lack of participants, the project later expanded to include writers who write for various and several fandoms such as Harry Potter, Undertale, Good Omens and Miraculous Ladybug. This allowed for a broader comparison of how fandom context shapes writing practice.

A total of ten interviews were conducted with writers of varying levels of popularity, age, and fandom affiliation. Despite their diversity, all participants shared one notable trait: they were avid readers growing up and mentioned a strong preference for fantasy literature.

¹¹ <https://www.marveltrumpshate.com/about/>

This shared cultural foundation offers valuable context for their narrative instincts and affective investments in fanfiction writing.

Participants generally encountered fandom spaces and fanfiction in adolescence, often starting as readers before transitioning into writing. The initial encounter was usually emotionally motivated: via a sense of lack in canon, peer influence, or the desire to explore stories more deeply. For many, fanfiction became an alternative creative outlet, offering emotional fulfilment, identity exploration, and a sense of belonging outside institutional literary norms.

Most participants articulated two key motivations: to complete or expand on what they felt canon left unfinished, and to derive emotional satisfaction through character or world exploration and storytelling. As Henry Jenkins notes, fanfiction often functions as a cultural repair mechanism where fans “poach” from the source material to mend, reinterpret, or emotionally deepen canonical narratives that feel insufficient (*Textual Poachers*, 1992). While all writers claimed to write for themselves, many admitted that audience feedback gradually shaped their practice. The transformation from writing into "the void" to having readers who expect updates or leave comments changed their sense of authorship over time. When we asked about how fanfiction changed their sense of self many replied by saying they are feeling like an author now or now they know that they can write and have an audience.

i. Community, Segmentation, and Hierarchies

Participants frequently highlighted that fandom is not a unified entity but a segmented, multi-layered space. Writers consistently spoke of belonging to specific Discord servers, ship groups, or friend circles within larger fandoms. For example, even within the Marvel fandom, the MTH group is seen as a distinct subculture with its own norms, rituals, and shared values:

“Marvel community is super, super supportive... many stuff has sort of been established in the fandom way before I ever joined it”

“most people are older... everybody is a professional in real life, most of us have kids. So we're all sort of in a similar head space. Most everybody is well educated”

“people are so kind... there is no drama no toxic traits unlike other fandoms I've been in”

In contrast, younger fandoms like *Miraculous Ladybug* were described as more prone to conflict and less moderated. Participants – when talking about other fandoms that they were used to in – usually made comparisons to other fandoms such as *Supernatural* or *Twilight* – pointed that the fans were usually younger and this cause more drama or ‘ship wars’. This generational split affects online interaction. Fandoms with older members are seen as calmer, kinder, and more professional, while younger oriented spaces are more emotionally intense or chaotic. When we were talking with writers of MTH group and asked why they are a calm and functional group they praised their moderators in the Discord server and pointed out the experience and age of their moderators.

In addition to age, the size and longevity of a fandom appeared to affect its internal consistency. Both *Harry Potter* and *Marvel* are 'mega-fandoms' - they have been around for decades, with millions of people producing discussions, theories, edits, fanworks, and critiques across various online platforms. As a result, these fandoms have developed highly stabilized interpretations of certain characters. Even in Alternate Universe fics, there is an unspoken consensus about how characters like Steve Rogers or Harry Potter should behave. These shared ideas seem more rigid and culturally embedded than in smaller or newer fandoms.

Although difficult to prove empirically, many participants implicitly referred to this when describing how deviations from these core characterizations must be narratively justified. Such as:

“I'm trying to base these differences in canon- so that it makes sense. And from what my fans tell me, these differences do make sense”

“even if I write a total complete AU, I just want them to be in character”

“you can write anything, like you can put them in any situation and you can make them behave any way as long as it's like justified”

The emotional accuracy expected from these portrayals speaks to a canon-like function of fanon itself, one shaped not by creators but by cumulative fan labor. In the case of mega-fandoms like *Harry Potter* and *Marvel*, this creates a hyperreal space where characters are stabilized through decades of repetition, reinterpretation, and emotional discourse. As Baudrillard suggests, meaning in a hyperreal system is no longer tied to an original source but to a chain of simulations. The 'real' Steve Rogers or Harry Potter is not the one in the films or

books, but the emotionally coherent figure produced by fan interactions, headcanons, and reified through thousands of works. As a writer put in: "I never read the books. Most of what I know comes from other fics or Tumblr discussions." Similarly, other one stated: "I only saw the movies once, I haven't read the comics or anything. I think I get most of it from Tumblr or fanfics." Some writers talked about how there are writers that they know who didn't even watch the movies but still are writing fanfics, similarly some of the writers we spoke with said that they are in some fandoms where they don't like the show but like reading their fanfics: "I watched the first season, it just not bad, but nothing I put my time to. But then I read a fan fiction that was just so amazing. And then I read everything, every single thing in that fandom. I still don't know how Canon works exactly." Many writers talked about similar experiences. They don't watch the show, read the comics but their first encounter with fandom happens by reading fanfiction. Their idea of the world of the characters come from an already simulated view.

These quotes illustrate how the original canon can become peripheral or even irrelevant to some writers. Their understanding of character is based on cumulative fanon exposure. Narratives shaped by and for the community.

This hyperreal orientation is reinforced by digital environments. Algorithms on platforms like Tumblr, Twitter, TikTok and even though it doesn't have an algorithm AO3 privilege emotionally resonant content — popular tropes, high-commented fics, or accepted head canons — which in turn stabilize specific character portrayals. New fans often enter the fandom through these algorithmically mediated encounters rather than the source text. What they first encounter as 'Truth' is often already a hyperreal construct.

Thus, the hyperreality of fanon is both community-driven and technologically reinforced. It represents a powerful cultural mechanism by which fandom sustains itself: not through fidelity to canon, but through the collective simulation of meaning. This reinforces the earlier point that fanon, in such environments, functions as a simulacrum: more emotionally valid and narratively plausible than the original.

Segmentation also took the form of ship-based identity. Writers emphasized that different ships have their own cultures, preferences, and even writing expectations. For instance in *Miraculous Ladybug* divides by their acceptance of the Character Adrien where one side finds him "wholesome, sweet" while other side finds him "rich and snobby". Just

like people who ship Steve/Tony versus Steve/Bucky in Marvel fandom have different ideas about the characters.

Finally, hierarchies were often implied rather than stated. Popular writers accumulate social capital through productivity, style, or community engagement, but overt competition is downplayed. While fandom is framed as egalitarian and welcoming, status circulates through comment counts, Big Bang participations, beta reader networks, and perceived emotional intelligence.

Still, we should point out that among the ten fanfiction writers interviewed, only two were widely recognized within their communities, and two others have somewhat consistent readership. The remaining six have limited visibility and low comment engagement, yet all 6 of them had written dozens of stories or have more than 100.000 words cumulatively each in their body of work.

This reflects as the participatory ethos of fan culture. Rather than chasing fame, these writers act on an affective investment (Jenkins, 1992) extending emotional engagement with characters into long-term narrative exploration. Their continued labor in the face of minimal external validation also supports Busse and Hellekson's idea of the gift economy: a space where writing is offered not for monetary return but as an act of care and connection.

Thus, while recognition structures exist, fanfiction is primarily a labor of love - a practice rooted in emotional attachment, creative persistence, and community-based meaning-making.

ii. Cultural Capital and What Makes a Writer "Popular" and What Makes Fanon Interpretations "Stick"

When asked what makes a fanfiction writer successful or respected, participants independently emphasized the same three components: good writing, the popular tropes, and the right timing. This informal but powerful triad forms the basis of what Pierre Bourdieu would call cultural capital in the fanfiction field.

Timing referred to moments when the fandom was particularly active or engaged such as when new movie is released or a fandom event brings people together. Writers emphasized the importance of publishing when the fandom is 'alive' or during periods of high emotional investment.

"I think sometimes it's just about when you post. Like if there's a movie coming out or something, more people are active and looking for fic."

"If you post at the right time, it can blow up. If you miss it, the same fic gets 10 kudos."

Tropes, especially emotionally satisfying ones, serve as shared symbolic references a kind of narrative currency. Whether it's "slow burn" or "enemies to lovers," tropes enable both the writer and reader to meet on common ground, amplifying emotional impact.

Popularity also includes a social dimension: being known in Discord spaces, engaging in comment sections, and participating in Big Bangs all contribute to one's visibility. High-output authors, such as those in the MTH community with 100+ fics, tend to gain prestige over time through a mix of productivity, community trust, and stylistic resonance. It's also important to point out that many participants said even though someone may not be a writer but if they discuss character, explain the world, create head canons—simply explain the world and story then they can become trustworthy and popular, can become *a fan with authority*. When asked directly what makes a fanon interpretation stick, the most frequent answer was that it fills in the gaps of canon. Fanon stays when it provides emotional or narrative coherence—when it explains plot holes, the story's world, ambiguous actions, or character behaviours.

In other words, consensus forms not just through repetition, but through explanatory power. When a headcanon resonates across multiple fics and helps stabilize the character emotionally or morally, it becomes part of the shared truth of the fandom.

This dual process—of reading before writing, and selecting emotionally satisfying explanations—illustrates how fanon becomes both infrastructure and inheritance. Writers do not create in a vacuum. They build on the fanon that came before them, internalizing emotional logics already circulating in the community.

These findings support Bourdieu's theory of symbolic economies: value is not financial but reputational, and prestige circulates through a mix of aesthetic fluency, consistency, and participation in community rituals (Hills, 2002).

iii. Fanfiction vs. Original Fiction and the Allure of Transformative Work

Several writers discussed their relationship to original fiction and why they choose to remain within fanfiction. While some had aspirations to write original stories, fanfiction remained the more emotionally accessible and fulfilling medium.

“with Fanfic, as long as one person likes it, the fan art has done his job”

"Fic is easier to finish. You already know the world and the characters."

“I think writing fan fiction is easier in a lot of ways because you have something to work off of. You have a world already, you have some characters already, you can play around with them and of course you can do really, really interesting stuff with.”

This sense of creative ease was echoed by others, who noted that fanfiction allows them to bypass world-building and character invention in favour of deep emotional arcs and stylistic experimentation. The pre-existing narrative offers stability and focus, especially for writers managing full-time jobs or parenting responsibilities.

The longevity and personal investment in a single universe contrasts sharply with the disposability often associated with online writing. Fanfiction, in this view, is not a stepping stone but a destination, a space for emotional endurance, community resonance, and creative self-definition.

These attitudes support the notion that transformative works are not necessarily preparatory. Rather, they offer a distinct form of creative practice that is valid and complete in itself. The choice to remain in fanfiction reflects not a lack of ambition, but a deliberate embrace of emotional resonance over institutional validation.

iv. Fanfiction and Everyday Resistance: Narratives, Censorship, and Representation

Although none of the participants explicitly described their work as political, every single one of them acknowledged that fanfiction holds power—whether through representation, normalization, or resistance to dominant narratives. Across all interviews, participants expressed a shared understanding that simply creating or sharing stories in today’s cultural climate is a political act.

Some pointed to structural issues around censorship, visibility, and the political implications of writing marginalized identities:

“Ao3 was created as a place for things to exist without censorship... because those advertisers would have an opinion and a censorships... When there's so much censorship happening around the world. It is definitely inherently political”

Others focused on the stakes of representation, especially in the context of queer identity and trans inclusion:

“Even I am kind of making a political statement with my fanfic, namely that everyone is a person, especially in the face of what J.K. Rowling is trying to tell people. I have trans characters in my story. I have non-human characters in my story that I do treat as just normal characters and as people. And I think that's the story that I want to convey with my fic.”

This cultural politics of emotion recurs in other testimonies:

“I think stories have a power... not just fanfic but all of our stories have a power to normalize things, to shape opinions.”

“I hope that it has a power. Because stories have a power—what kind of stories are told. It doesn't have to be an original to have an impact.”

Notably, participants consistently framed political potential not through large-scale societal transformation, but through smaller acts of normalization and ideological disruption. The writers do not view fanfiction as inherently radical, but recognize that it can function as a space for reframing cultural norms. Especially when these norms are hostile to queer identities, to empathy, or to creative autonomy.

Taken together, these reflections suggest that fanfiction is not only embedded in broader political structures, it is also an ongoing negotiation of cultural meaning, emotional resonance, and representational power. This is not politics in the grand ideological sense but as negotiations of discourse, privilege, and visibility. And, in Ahmed's (2004) framework, these stories circulate affectively: they teach readers what to feel, how to care, and whom to see as human. These emotional reversals open space for alternative politics: of care, of fragility, of mutual recognition. Even the act of writing queer romance in a heteronormative canon constitutes a form of resistance, whether intended or not.

Moreover, by refusing commodification—by writing and publishing for free, for an audience of peers—fanfiction writers also refuse neoliberal metrics of value.

“Pressure (to write an original story) only comes from people who I talk about this within real life who aren't fans. Because I think if you are in fandom, you kind of get it. That it has value. It's not just something that you do for nothing. You sort of creating something that you hope other people will enjoy and to get some joy back. This feedback loop of you put something out there, people enjoy it, makes you feel good - and it makes you want to make people feel good more. It's like a continuous cycle.”

“I think the joy of writing is even more prominent than with original stories because you aren't doing it for money.”

Fanfiction can be seen as a practice of radical imagination. Writers explore what is not allowed in canon whether it's alternate relationships, dark character arcs, or deeply personal healing narratives. These are political choices in their own right, rooted in the cultural politics of emotion (Ahmed, 2004): how certain feelings, bodies, and desires are made visible or invisible.

Even within community structures like MTH, the collaborative ethos based on gifting, auctioning for charity, and co-creation points toward alternative economies of value. Prestige in fandom does not come from money but from emotional resonance, consistency, and generosity.

Thus, fanfiction is not simply a hobby. It is a cultural practice that reveals how affect and narrative are interwoven with political meaning, even when those meanings remain unspoken.

v. The Canon-Fanon Tension and Hyperreality of Baudrillard

One of the most compelling insights from the fieldwork was the way writers conceptualize canon and fanon. Even when stories are set in Alternate Universes (AUs), participants consistently emphasized the importance of staying emotionally consistent with the character. As several explained:

"You can go AU, but it has to be earned."

"If I'm writing a dark fic, I want to know why they became this person."

"The character has to match with the character in my head."

Writers explained that characters in fanfiction can be radically altered—as long as their emotional logic is internally consistent. A Steve Rogers who is cruel, or a Harry Potter who becomes morally gray, must have a reason that fits the emotional framework established by the fanon. As an interviewee noted:

"Even if Steve Rogers is an asshole, the writer must give a reason — what made him become that way."

The phrase “the character in my head” appeared frequently, highlighting that writers are not writing toward canon but toward a shared emotional impression. A composite constructed through years of fanfiction, Tumblr discourse, head canons, memes, and community conversations. Like we explained in previous parts many writers noted that they themselves are part of fandoms that they never seen the original work of. Their first encounter happens through fanfiction – accepted fanon version not canon work.

This is where Jean Baudrillard’s concept of hyperreality becomes essential. According to Baudrillard, a third-order simulacrum is a copy with no original—an image or model that refers only to other copies. Fanon, in this sense, is not a distortion of canon but a self-contained symbolic system. The “truth” of the character no longer comes from the original text but from accumulated community consensus.

For example, in the Marvel fandom, Tony Stark is often portrayed as anxious, self-sacrificing, and soft-hearted. Even though these qualities are only subtly suggested in the source material. Of course, it is the richness and charisma of the canon that created the fandom in the first place. The professional work of actors, screenwriters, and directors provides the foundation upon which fandom builds. However, when we asked writers whether the fanon version is “more real,” all emphasized that none of it is real. All is fiction. These characters belong to franchises written by dozens of people across different media, styles, and creative visions. What fandom does, they explain, is provide continuity, care, and emotional coherence, and depth. The fandom gives these characters the labour they need to become fuller, more psychologically layered figures. Through this sustained collective effort, Tony Stark becomes a three-dimensional character worthy of thousands of fanfics. The fanon Tony becomes the ‘true Tony’ not by replacing canon, but by emotionally completing it. Especially

when writers and readers share a consensus about the internal logic of his decisions. One of our interviewees explained how the fandom made the Tony Stark character three-dimensional.

“Yes, Tony's smart in the movies. But, you know, fandom will build on that and talk about what that means and how isolating that can be to be that intelligent, how much pressure he puts on himself, how he expects so much of himself that he can't fail. He has to solve everything... we can give that depth to a very basic characterization that Tony's smart”

Each writer underlined that even in Alternate Universe settings—coffee shop AUs, fantasy crossovers, or modern re-imaginings—the character’s emotional essence must remain legible. The fic may take place in a world where Harry Potter is in Slytherin or Steve Rogers is a single dad who has a tattoo parlour in Brooklyn or the complete opposite and he is an arrogant and rude person , but the emotional logic that underpins their behaviour must still “feel right.”. If he is portrayed as emotionally distant or volatile, the narrative must still make it coherent.

This affective standard constructs a fanon truth that replaces canonical authority. Writers are not beholden to canon, they are beholden to plausibility within the fan-discursive system. The original text becomes secondary, referenced only indirectly through shared emotion, tone, and character affect.

In this way, fanfiction becomes a hyperreal text. It copies not the canon but previous fanfictions, headcanons, social media commentaries, and fanarts. Its meaning is maintained not by fidelity to a source, but by coherence within a simulation. A Steve Rogers who was never written this way in the MCU still “feels” right in fanfiction, because that version of him has been emotionally stabilized by the community.

Many writers talked about certain writers who write fanfiction without even reading / watching canon, many writers told that they themselves read fanfiction without encountering canon. There are many people who are not invested in Harry Potter but its canon-divergence¹² stories such as All The Young Dudes and the story of one of our interviewee’s. There are people who write fanfiction based on these fanfictions and their original characters. This is

¹² “canon divergence” is primarily a fandom term, used when fanfiction is set in a universe that diverges from the original canon due to changing a character's backstory or the plot overall

the final consequence of hyperreality: the character becomes detached from any need for an original text. They are real not because they are canonical, but because they have achieved narrative realism within the hyperreal system.

In fanfiction, canon becomes the myth of origin. It is cited, referenced, and reworked but it does not govern the logic of meaning. What governs is emotion, community, and simulation. The result is a fan culture that is not just transformative it is generative. It produces entire symbolic systems that feel more emotionally truthful than the texts they reference.

One writer provided a particularly rich case. They are the author of a long-running Harry Potter fanfic – a retelling of the whole series - that has become so influential that people are writing fanfics of their fanfic. The story has began January 2022, it's currently in year-3 of Harry Potter universe, has a cumulative of 1,144,480 word count and a total of 1.549.547 hits¹³.

Their work has accrued such symbolic weight that it has become a referential center in its own right. They operate a Discord server of around 1,000 people dedicated specifically to their story. The server functions like a small town, with channels for meta discussion, head canons, memes, and even fanart and of their own work. In other words, their story has become a space of fandom—a world within a world.

This phenomenon mirrors what happened with *All the Young Dudes* (ATYD), the massively popular Harry Potter fanfic that rewrote the Marauders' timeline and established an entire emotional canon around characters like Sirius Black and Remus Lupin. In both cases, we see what Baudrillard would call a third-order simulacrum: the writer's version of the characters becomes more culturally relevant than the original. In the case of this writer, their fanfic story has not only been emotionally accepted as canon but is now being built upon by other creators. The character arcs, timelines, and world-building choices they established are treated as foundational truths. The writer notes:

“I'm hearing that about my characters a lot as well, and people say, oh that is the only version I will now accept.”

What this shows is that fanon can evolve into a new canon. Their Discord server does not simply discuss their fic—they inhabit it. The space becomes a hyperreal simulation, where

¹³ <https://archiveofourown.org/series/2696020>

the original Harry Potter books are only one layer in a much larger, more emotionally resonant mythos.

The author has become the myth-maker of a subcanon. This is not transformation—it is generative authorship. Their work is not an extension of Harry Potter; it is a parallel world that readers opt into, emotionally and communally.

This phenomenon perfectly illustrates hyperreality. The original no longer governs the character—the emotional consensus formed around the simulacrum does. In this way, fanfiction doesn't just reimagine a canon text; it constructs an entirely new symbolic order, one that is more lived, more debated, and more emotionally coherent than the official product.

This is Baudrillard's Disneyland: the fiction that reveals how all other fictions are constructed. And in fanfiction culture, that construction is collaborative, affective, and always in motion. Fanfiction, then, operates under a different epistemology: one where truth is emotional, social, and discursively constructed, not fixed by origin. Hyperreality is not a breakdown of meaning, but a reinvention of meaning through affective precision and communal simulation.

Baudrillard's theory thus provides a powerful framework to describe the fanfiction economy as a simulacral order. In this order, characters function not as extensions of canon but as affective signifiers. They are shaped and validated through repetition, reinterpretation, and community consensus. The result is a form of narrative realism rooted in plausibility and emotional continuity rather than authorial authority. As fanon replaces canon as the dominant symbolic order, the fanfic text becomes a copy that refers only to other copies: other fanfics, head canons, Tumblr posts, and Discord chats. And yet, it feels more real than the original. In this symbolic order, fanon does not need legitimacy from canon—it produces its own.

GENERAL SYNTHESIS

Ultimately, this fieldwork reveals fanfiction as a collaborative simulation in which meaning is produced not by fidelity to a singular origin, but by the intensity of shared emotional truth. Writers operate within a symbolic order where canon becomes a starting point, not a final authority—subverted, extended, or rewritten through collective negotiation. In this space, the “real” is not what was written by creators, but what feels emotionally justified, plausible, and resonant to readers and writers alike. Fanon, then, becomes more than

an alternative reading; it is a socially constructed and affectively stabilized reality. Through this lens, fanfiction is not only a literary practice but also a discursive site where cultural meaning, emotional politics, and symbolic legitimacy are constantly reshaped. It is, in Baudrillard's terms, the hyperreal made manifest—an ecosystem of fictions that reveals how all realities, even canonical ones, are themselves constructed, contested, and negotiated.

CONCLUSION

In the age of participatory culture and platform-based storytelling, fanfiction represents a key site for analysing how cultural meaning, narrative authority, and emotional legitimacy are negotiated outside traditional institutions. This thesis has taken fanfiction not as an anecdotal or marginal cultural activity, but as a serious discursive field in which writers produce, distribute, and reshape meaning—often in dialogue with massive transmedia franchises. Through an in-depth field study based on ten semi-structured interviews with fanfiction writers—primarily from the Marvel and Harry Potter fandoms—this research has explored how characters are collectively interpreted, how emotional truths are prioritized over canonical ones, and how digital community structures shape symbolic authority. The guiding theoretical framework of this analysis has been Jean Baudrillard’s concept of hyperreality, supported by insights from Michel Foucault, Pierre Bourdieu, Henry Jenkins, and Kristina Busse.

One of the central contributions of this thesis lies in demonstrating how fanon—a community-constructed understanding of characters—can displace canonical representations through processes of emotional coherence, communal labour, and affective circulation. Particularly within mega-fandoms like Marvel and Harry Potter, these alternative interpretations are not only widespread, but often more stable and more emotionally resonant than the “original” texts. Interview participants repeatedly emphasized that even when writing within Alternate Universes (AUs), emotional consistency and narrative justification were non-negotiable.

This insistence on narrative plausibility—even within fictional reimaginings—matches Baudrillard’s order of simulacra: where the copy no longer refers to an original but to an internal system of signs. In such a system, the fanon Tony Stark—soft-hearted, anxious, emotionally burdened—is not merely a deviation from canon, but the emotionally legitimate Tony Stark. Writers and readers agree upon this version not because it is true to the script or the director’s intent, but because it makes sense within the logic of accumulated fanworks, affective discourse, and communal reinforcement.

These patterns suggest that fanfiction spaces operate as **hyperreal environments**, where the emotional realism of characters overrides fidelity to source material. Participants described entering fandom through Tumblr edits, AO3 tags, or headcanon discussions—long

before or instead of engaging with the canon itself. Some openly stated they had never read the original books or only watched the films once. In this context, what Baudrillard describes as the precession of simulacra is evident: characters like Tony Stark and Steve Rogers or Harry Potter no longer refer to original texts, but to a system of emotional expectations and affective norms built by the fandom.

The fieldwork also revealed how cultural capital operates within fandom. Drawing from Bourdieu, this thesis examined how symbolic prestige is accumulated through productivity, aesthetic fluency, timing, and participation in community rituals like Big Bangs or Discord servers. When asked what makes a writer “popular,” nearly all participants identified the same three criteria: good writing, the right tropes, and publishing at the right time. This reveals how visibility and resonance are tied not to inherent literary quality, but to contextual factors that are socially and algorithmically mediated. We further examined how fan prestige is earned, circulated, and contested—not merely through technical writing skill but through emotional labor, interpretive coherence, and communal alignment. Writers who successfully “get the character right” are not simply rewarded for mimicking canon, but for reinforcing a fanon version stabilized by collective emotional consensus. As Sara Ahmed reminds us, feelings are not just private responses but public orientations; in fan communities, they become politically potent tools that rewrite what matters, who matters, and why.

Moreover, the symbolic power of fanon was most visible in the testimony of an interviewee, a Harry Potter writer whose long-form fic gathered over 500,000 readers and birthed its own sub-fandom. The feedback loop of community affirmation, citation, and recursive creation produces what Baudrillard would call a “referential hallucination”—a simulated reality whose legitimacy is secured not through origin, but through emotional truth.

While the prestige of such writers is often discussed in fandom spaces, the majority of the writers interviewed are largely unknown. They wrote not for fame, but for personal fulfillment, emotional processing, and narrative exploration. This echoes what Jenkins calls the *gift economy* of fan communities, where labour is not commodified but shared as an act of love and mutual recognition. These writers express what Busse (2015) identifies as *affective fan labor*: a gendered and often invisible form of emotional and narrative work that sustains communities, even without visibility or reward.

Politically, fanfiction also emerges as a space of resistance. While not all writers described their work as overtly political, many articulated a quiet defiance in their choice of

themes, characters, or relationships. “Even writing queer fluff is political when the world says it shouldn’t exist,” said one. Another described including trans and non-human characters simply as “people,” contrasting this with J.K. Rowling’s politics. These micro-political acts align with Sara Ahmed’s notion of *the cultural politics of emotion*—how feelings are not apolitical, but are socially distributed, regulated, and contested. In writing vulnerable, queer, or emotionally complex stories, these writers challenge dominant scripts about gender, power, and morality.

This thesis has also demonstrated that fanfiction communities are not monolithic. The MTH (Marvel Trumps Hate) subgroup, for example, is older, more organized, and characterized by a collaborative ethos rooted in charity, gifting, and emotional solidarity. Its members describe the group as calm, kind, and generationally stable. In contrast, younger fandoms such were described as more volatile, emotional, and prone to ship-based conflict. These differences highlight how age, platform culture, and genre shape the emotional and social structure of fandom.

The segmentation of fandom also reinforces the hyperreal structure of fanon. Within different ships, characterizations can radically differ—yet each version is stabilized by the community that shares and repeats it. What emerges, then, is not one canon but multiple coexisting *subcanons*, each legitimated through emotional consistency and communal discourse.

The study also asked: what makes certain fanon interpretations “stick”? The answer, it seems, is not just affect, but explanation. Participants reported that headcanons which “make things make sense”—filling plot holes, explaining character choices, or resolving inconsistencies—were more likely to be adopted. These interpretive tools allow fan communities to build *subcultural coherence*—a shared epistemology that privileges emotional realism over textual fidelity.

In reflecting on the broader implications of this work, one must also consider the limitations. The sample, while diverse in age, gender, and fandom, was primarily drawn from English-speaking and Tumblr-based communities. A more global analysis might reveal different narrative logics, affective norms, or symbolic hierarchies. Moreover, the focus on interviews—while providing rich qualitative insight—could be complemented by textual analysis of the fanworks themselves in future studies.

Nevertheless, this research contributes to fan studies by demonstrating that **fanfiction is a cultural field in its own right**—complete with rules, norms, hierarchies, and systems of legitimacy. It is a space where readers become writers, where emotional truth supersedes authorial intent, and where collective imagination generates new symbolic orders. Through the lens of hyperreality, we see that fanfiction does not merely copy canon—it produces something else entirely: a simulated truth that feels more stable, more emotionally just, and more “real” to those who inhabit it.

Fanfiction, then, is not a supplement to media culture—it is one of its most revealing manifestations. It shows how meaning is made, how stories gain power, and how communities sustain themselves through affective labor. In its collaborative construction of character, its resistance to commodification, and its deep emotional infrastructure, fanfiction represents not just a literary form, but a cultural and political act.

In this sense, the fanfiction writer is not simply a fan or a consumer. They are an author, a theorist, a historian, and a builder of hyperrealities. And the fandom? It is not a passive audience but a machine of simulation, care, and meaning-making—one that rewrites the rules of authorship, community, and cultural legitimacy.

Taken together, these insights suggest that the politics of canon is not about protecting the integrity of a source text, but about controlling which realities are permitted to exist. In resisting that control, fans become not just readers or writers, but worldbuilders of a new symbolic order. As digital platforms continue to reshape the boundaries of cultural production, the fanon simulacrum will only grow more powerful—offering alternative futures, healing narratives, and new modes of collective authorship.

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